

Creating Workflows for Building, Managing, and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages: Challenges, Approaches, and Lessons Learned

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Abstract [EN]

The article describes the workshop “Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages”: its motivations, methods, challenges, and outcomes. The latter include four workflows, that are described here and have been published online in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace. The article also highlights the importance of having good, available, FAIR and CARE data for textual corpora in under-resourced languages throughout the entire lifecycle of the corpus, providing context and further perspectives.

Abstract [DE]

Der Beitrag stellt den Workshop „Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages“ vor: seine Gründe, Methoden, Herausforderungen und Ergebnisse. Letztere umfassen vier Arbeitsabläufe, die im Artikel beschrieben werden, und die online im “Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace” verfügbar sind. Betont wird überdies die Bedeutung guter, verfügbarer, FAIR- und CARE-konformer Daten für Textkorpora in unterrepräsentierten Sprachen während des gesamten Lebenszyklus des Textkorpus. Auch werden der Kontext und die künftigen Perspektiven angesprochen.

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Introduction

From the 28th to the 30th of August 2024, DARIAH working groups on Research Data Management and Multilingual Digital Humanities join their forces to organise a hybrid workshop, supported by the DARIAH Working Groups Funding Call 2023-25.² The aim was to develop workflows describing the main steps for the creation, management and archiving of multilingual corpora.³ A diverse crowd of practitioners with background in research data management, digital humanities (DH), computational linguistics, and library science, and research software engineering⁴ came to Hamburg in Germany or joined the event online to share their expertise and solutions to the many challenges faced by those who want to build digital corpora for under-represented languages. After two days of presentations and exchanges, the participants prepared on the last third day some four workflows that have been published in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace,⁵ promoting and enabling the sharing of methodologies and best practices when compiling FAIR and machine-readable corpora.⁶

Motivation and Importance of Multilingual Digital Humanities

Text analysis is central in the humanities, and building textual corpora is often one of the first steps in most digital humanities projects. The more data can be included in the corpus, the more new perspectives can be explored. In addition, the quantity of data also influences the quality of most computational analysis, especially when machine learning is involved.⁷ Because scholarly and industrial attention has been given predominantly to English, and more

²<https://www.dariah.eu/2024/04/03/dariah-working-groups-funding-call-2023-meet-the-winning-projects/> [Retrieved 31 October, 2024].

³ Regarding our choice of terminology and the use of ‘multilingualism’, we follow here the practice of Viola, L., & Spence, P. (Eds.). (2023). *Multilingual Digital Humanities* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696>, see in particular the introduction, p. 4.

⁴ We would like to express our special thanks to our participants who contributed to the workshop in person or online: Françoise Gouzi, Martin Wynne, Péter Király, Cristina Vertan, Shih-Pei Chen, Calvin Yeh, Alexander König, Aleksandr Riaposov, Alexandre Arkhipov, Jonas Müller-Laackman, Gardy Stein, Elena Lazarenko, Till Grallert, Nanette Ribler-Pipka, Monika Xenia Kudela, Paul Spence, Femmy Admiraal, Alessia Spadi, Emiliano Degl’Innocenti, Georgios Vardakis, Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio, and Duncan Paterson. Our special thanks go as well to Merve Tekgürler, co-chair of the ADHO Multilingual DH SIG and one of the workshop presenters, for their thoughtful contribution to the conceptualization of the workshop.

⁵ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?categories=workflow&order=label> [Retrieved October 31, 2024].

⁶ Gouzi, F. (16 September 2024). Workflows for Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages. *DARIAH Open*. Retrieved October 31, 2024 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/12b2b>.

⁷ We will not go into detail about the machine learning side and refer to the extended discussion in Fekete, M. R., et al. “Typological Challenges for the Application of Multilingual Language Models in the Digital Humanities.” In Viola, L., & Spence, P. (Eds.). (2023). *Multilingual Digital Humanities* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696>, pp. 148.

particularly the modern English of social media,⁸ most digital corpora, methods, and tools for the pre- and post-processing of textual data have often not been adapted to other languages and scripts. The relevant existing scholarship has also pointed out the severe lack of tools that could reliably help extract multilingual and non-English data which results in the uneven representation or even absence of digital data available for these languages.⁹ This is also a problem because the lack of digital visibility relegates these languages and scripts to a neglected status, reducing the likelihood of them becoming the focus of tool development, which further strengthens their marginalisation, creating a sort of vicious circle. A narrow form of English is thus over-represented, while most other languages fall in the background. This downward spiral does not facilitate linguistic diversity and inclusion and does not represent the rich linguistic diversity that exists in the non-digital world. The workshop addressed this gap by focusing on multilingual DH, emphasising the importance of creating equitable and accessible digital resources for all languages.

Moreover, the workshop aimed to further develop on the topic of research data management for multilingual data, as it was tackled in a nutshell by the DARIAH Working Group on Research Data Management in one previous research project¹⁰, mainly pursuing two research

⁸ Of course, we are aware that English is not one and has multiple variations which can present different levels of challenges in the context of DH - creole English presents a case in point as Setsuko Yokoyama pointed out as part of a mini-conference on multilingual DH, co-organized by the ADHO Multilingual DH Special Interest Group and the DARIAH Multilingual DH Working Group under the auspices of the DH2024 conference in Washington DC.

⁹ See Dombrowski Q. & Burns P. “Language Is Not a Default Setting: Countering DH’s English Problem” In Gold M.K. & Klein L.F. (Eds) (2023). *Debates in the Digital Humanities*. University of Minnesota Press. <https://dhdebates.gc.cuny.edu/read/debates-in-the-digital-humanities-2023/section/704fd8ae-99f1-4bfc-a275-7f5ad88b48af>; Horvath A. “Digital Brush Talk: Challenges and Potential Connections in East Asian Digital Research.” In: Fiormonte D., Ricaurte Quijano P. & Chaudhuri S., (Eds.) *Global Debates in the Digital Humanities*. University of Minnesota Press. (2022): 127-140.; Spence, P. and Brandao R. “Towards Language Sensitivity and Diversity in the Digital Humanities.” *Digital Studies/Le champ numérique* (2021) 11(1): 9, pp. 1–29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.8098>; Gil A. & Ortega É. “Global Outlooks in Digital Humanities: Multilingual Practices and Minimal Computing.” *Doing Digital Humanities: Practice, Training, Research*. Crompton C. Lane R. J., Siemens R. (Eds.) (2016) Routledge. 22-34.; Horvath A., van Lit C., Wagner C. & Wrisley D. “Towards Multilingually Enabled Digital Knowledge Infrastructures – A Survey Analysis” In: Viola, Lorella and Paul Spence, eds. *Multilingual Digital Humanities*. Routledge. (2024): 197-212.; Horvath A., van Lit C., Wagner C. & Wrisley D. “Centering Multilingual Users: Thinking through UX Personas in the DH Community.” *Digital Studies/Le champ numérique* (2024) in “DH Unbound 2022, Selected Papers,” eds. Bordalejo B., Risam R., & Château-Dutier E. 13(3): 1–30.. <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.9608>; Malínek V., Umerle T., Gray E., Heibi I., Király P., Klaes C., Korytkowski P., Lindemann D., Moretti A., Panušková C., Péter R., Tolonen M., Tomczyńska A., Vimr O. “Open Bibliographical Data Workflows and the Multilinguality Challenge”, *Journal of Open Humanities Data* (2024) 10:27, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.190>

¹⁰ See Buelinckx E., Gelati F. & Király P., “3.2. Challenges in multilingualism” in E. Tóth-Czifra et al., ‘Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community’ (DARIAH, 30 August 2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8059626> or https://gitlab-ce.rrz.uni-hamburg.de/uahh-digitale-dienste/rdm-for-arts-and-humanities/-/blob/master/part-03.md?ref_type=heads#32-challenges-in-multilingualism.

axes: data quality¹¹ and standardisation¹² of textual corpora. Finally, the workshop wanted to facilitate exchange and cross-fertilisation of expertise between Europe’s two main research infrastructures for humanities, thanks to the presence of specialists researchers from both DARIAH and CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure).¹³

Focus on Under-Represented Languages: A word on our terminology

A key lesson learned during the workshop was the importance of nuance in the wordings that we utilised when referring to our target languages. This led us to often refer to “under-represented languages”, rather than “under-resourced” or “non-English”, to include the languages that are marginalised but not necessarily under-resourced such as Chinese, and various forms of English that deviate from the mainstream English. By including these diverse linguistic forms, the workshop aimed to broaden the scope of digital humanities and ensure a more inclusive representation of global linguistic diversity.

While we include all under-represented languages, we took care of considering the particular challenges faced by under-resourced languages. These languages often lack the necessary digital resources and infrastructure, making it difficult for those working with these languages to create comprehensive digital corpora. The workshop addressed these challenges by developing workflows that are adaptable to different linguistic contexts, providing a framework that can be tailored to the specific needs of each language. The workflows also serve as a guideline for institutions to make sure they provide the necessary support (financial and technical) to create sustainable corpora for under-represented and, in particular, under-resourced languages. Without targeted institutional support, these languages that are out of the radar of the industry and mainstream funding cannot occupy their place in the digital landscape.

Challenges in Corpus Creation for Under-Represented Languages

¹¹ See: Király P., ‘Measuring Metadata Quality’ (Göttingen: Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Doctoral Thesis, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.53846/goediss-7578>.

¹² See: Mattern E., ‘The Linguistic Data Life Cycle, Sustainability of Data, and Principles of Solid Data Management’, in *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management*, ed. Andrea L. Berez-Kroeker et al. (Cambridge Mass.: The MIT Press, 2022), 61–72, <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0009>.

¹³ About DARIAH, see Edmond J. et al., ‘9. Springing the Floor for a Different Kind of Dance: Building DARIAH as a Twenty-First-Century Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities’, in Eadem (Ed.), *Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research* (Cambridge, UK: Open Book Publishers, 2020), 207–34, <https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0192.09>. About CLARIN, see: Fišer D. and Witt A. (Eds.), *CLARIN: The Infrastructure for Language Resources* (De Gruyter, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110767377>.

Creating, managing, and archiving corpora for under-represented languages involve unique challenges that the workshop revealed in detail. These languages often lack the digital infrastructure and resources that are readily available for more widely spoken languages. Some of the key challenges, which repeatedly appeared throughout the presentations at the workshop, include the following:

- **Data Scarcity:** As Alíz Horváth pointed out in her “un-keynote keynote speech”¹⁴ on the first day of the workshop, there is often a lack of digitised (ie. OCR’ed and HTR’ed) texts available for these languages, which makes corpus creation difficult. This problem often stems from the lack of available, accessible, and well-functioning text recognition tools which forces scholars to handle an exceedingly high amount of manual corrections in the output. This may result in the delayed launch of DH projects in under-represented languages or may even cause scholars to abandon their project idea due to the excessive amount of necessary pre-processing work. It is thus clear that corpus building begins with and requires effective text recognition methods.
- **Linguistic Diversity:** Many under-represented languages have numerous dialects and variations (also depending on the time period when the texts were produced) and may use non-Latin scripts, which need to be accurately represented in digital corpora and, as Péter Király’s talk also emphasised, relevant multilingual metadata standards.¹⁵ Projects, such as Closing the Gap in non-Latin script data and LoGaRT (Local Gazetteers Research Tools for classical Chinese) introduced by Xenia Kudela, as well as Shih-Pei Chen and Calvin Yeh respectively, aim to remedy this problem by collecting data on non-Latin-script-based (particularly Arabic) digital projects, for the former, and by offering a comprehensive platform to access, analyse, and visualise digitised premodern Chinese local gazetteers, for the latter.¹⁶
- **Technical Limitations:** The presentations of Cristina Vertan and Alessia Spadi and Emiliano Degl’Innocenti both explored innovative tools (such as CLARIN tools) for

¹⁴ Alíz Horváth’s “unkeynote keynote speech” titled “What is a Corpus/Data/Workflow in a Multilingual Context? Why a Workflow for Non-English Sources? Rationale Behind the Workshop” took place on day 1 of the workshop (28 August 2024).

¹⁵ Péter Király’s presentation, “Multilingual Metadata Standards and Metrics through Europeana,” was part of the panel on “Metadata, Corpus Building” on day 1 (28 August 2024).

¹⁶ These presentations also allowed us to gain a more holistic view on how the complex process of corpus building and management operates in the context of concrete case studies. The talks were held as part of the panel “Putting it all together” on day 2 of the workshop: “Closing the Gap in non-Latin script data” by Xenia Kudela (who substituted Jonas Müller-Laackman) and “LoGaRT - Local Gazetteers Research Tools for classical Chinese” presented by Shih-Pei Chen and Calvin Yeh (29 August 2024).

corpus processing that can also handle multiple languages.¹⁷ On the other hand, existing digital tools and software may not support the scripts or linguistic features of these languages, necessitating the development of new tools or the adaptation of existing ones. An added issue here, as Till Grallert and Merve Tekgürler also pointed out in their respective presentations, often stems from the relative lack of support, which forces scholars to take up the heavy task of attempting to overcome obstacles on their own.¹⁸

- **Cultural Sensitivity:** Care (as well as the CARE principles¹⁹) must be taken to respect the cultural and historical contexts of these languages, especially when they are tied to indigenous or marginalised communities.²⁰ These points were also addressed by the presentations of Aleksandr Riaposov and Alexandre Arkhipov on managing corpora in minority languages and that of Georgios Vardakis and Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio on the linguistic aspects of annotated corpus creation for Corfioto.²¹
- **Assessments:** When deciding whether to develop new tools or adapt existing ones, scholars should ideally be able to compare the results, but the absence of benchmarks prevents them from assessing the potential improvement; and the same is true for assessing a new tool developed for an under-represented language.
- **Funding:** Under-represented languages are often under-resourced and need special attention from institutions that are not profit-driven.
- **Sustainability:** The lack of funding also affects the sustainability of the work with under-resourced languages, which cannot always be stored or preserved in the *longue durée*²². Relevant talks by Francesco Gelati on aspects to consider regarding archiving

¹⁷ Cristina Vertan’s talk “Corpus-Processing with CLARIN Tools,” and the presentation by Alessia Spadi and Emiliano Degl’Innocenti on “Tools for Corpus Processing” were included in the initial panel on day 2, titled “Corpus Processing”. (29 August 2024).

¹⁸ These presentations were held on day 1 of the workshop in the panel on “Metadata, Corpus Building”: “Corpus Building from Open, Collaborative and Scholarly Digital Editions” by Till Grallert and “An Ottoman Corpus: How to Think of Existing Materials as Data” by Merve Tekgürler (28 August 2024).

¹⁹ See: Carroll, S, et al. 2020. “The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance”. *Data Science Journal*, 19: XX, pp. 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-042>. See also: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>.

²⁰ On how the long-term research project “INEL – Grammatiken, Korpora und Sprachtechnologie für indigene nordeurasische Sprachen” tackled issues like cultural sensitivity, responsibility and ethics see: Ferger, A., “Processing Language Resources of Under-Resourced and Endangered Languages for the Generation of Argumentative Alternative Communication Boards” in *Proceedings of the 12th Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)*, p. 2644-2648, <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lrec-1.322.pdf>.

²¹ These presentations took place on day 2 within the framework of the panel on “Managing Minority and Endangered Language Corpora”: “Workflows for Managing Digital Corpora of Minority Languages” by Aleksandr Riaposov and Alexandre Arkhipov and “Seeking Contact-Induced Syntactic Change in Endangered Languages: A Methodology for Building a Morphosyntactically Annotated Corpus for Corfioto” by Georgios Vardakis and Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio. (29 August 2024)

²² See Gelati, F. “Archiving Textual Corpora: a Workflow and its Metadata” in *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal* 1 (under review).

corpora, particularly from the perspective of research data management, as well as Alexander König's talk on depositing corpora within the CLARIN framework both offered valuable insights, which inspired the third workflow on Archiving Textual Corpora.²³

Workshop Outcomes and Contributions

Our workshop provided a platform for practitioners from diverse backgrounds to share their expertise and solution in tackling the challenges mentioned above. Over the course of two and a half days, participants engaged in discussions and hands-on sessions that culminated in the creation of four comprehensive workflows. These workflows are designed to guide researchers through the process of creating, managing, and archiving corpora in any language, ensuring adherence to both the FAIR and CARE principles. They too contribute in addressing the conspicuous absence of pedagogical materials for computer-based textual examination in under-represented languages.²⁴ Furthermore they follow the minimal computing approach

The FAIR principles—Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability—are well-established guidelines that ensure data is managed in a way that maximises its utility and accessibility. However, in the context of multilingual and under-represented languages, it is equally important to consider the CARE principles: Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics.²⁵ These principles emphasise the need to respect the rights and interests of the communities from which the data originates, ensuring that the data management practices do not exploit or marginalise these communities but instead contribute to their empowerment and benefit. With the open-access workflows that we have created, we directly apply and enhance the 'be FAIR and take CARE' approaches to digital data management.

²³ These presentations concluded the program before the collaborative writing sprint and took place on day 3 as part of the panel "Corpora Archiving": "Archiving Textual Corpora" by Francesco Gelati and "Depositing Corpora within CLARIN" by Alexander König. (30 August 2024)

²⁴ For more inspiring examples see the review provided in Goodale, I. "Pedagogy and Praxis in Libraries: Natural Language Processing for Non-English Texts." In: Viola, L., & Spence, P. (Eds.). (2023). *Multilingual Digital Humanities* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696>, pp. 104.

²⁵ Carroll, S.R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O.L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., Parsons, M., Raseroka, K., Rodriguez-Lonebear, D., Rowe, R., Sara, R., Walker, J.D., Anderson, J. and Hudson, M. (2020) 'The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance', *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p. 43. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>.

The success of the workshop can be measured through the openly accessible publication of the four workflows in the SSH Open Marketplace.²⁶ They not only promote the sharing of best practices and points to consider but also serve as resources for future projects aiming to compile machine-readable corpora. By making these workflows publicly available, the workshop has contributed to a growing repository of knowledge that can be leveraged by researchers worldwide.

Based upon the abundance of aspects to consider during the process of building, managing, and archiving textual corpora, we have decided to produce multiple workflows corresponding to the major stages of the procedure - and also the overarching structure of the workshop which began with an extensive introduction to the interface and functionalities of the SSH Open Marketplace (with Alexander König as our guide),²⁷ and multiple panels with presentations on corpus creation on day 1, followed by further lively panels on corpus management and archiving on day 2, culminating in a collaborative workflow writing sprint in small groups on day 3. Each panel and the extensive discussion sections afterwards concentrated not only on the question of “What?”, that is the nature of the individual projects that the participants had created, but, equally importantly, on the “How?”, referring to the practical steps they took to create their projects and the lessons learned throughout the journey. All this meant to help us collect all relevant points at the end of each day as inspirations and workable case studies to be utilised during the compilations of the workflows.

The first two workflows cover the creation and the management of textual corpora for under-resourced languages. They specifically address the issues at stake when resources are lacking to build a digital corpus that is accurate, accessible, as well as sustainably curated and maintained: this explains why aspects such as OCR (Optical Character Recognition)-related issues, data quality, metadata standards, licensing, and ethics play a key role in both workflows. The third workflow on archiving digital corpora focuses on the sustainable

²⁶ See: Building Textual Corpora for Under-resourced Languages:

<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/67KJnp>

Managing Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages:

<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/fbXfuH>

Archiving Textual Corpora: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/gDzIoY>

Preparing minority or endangered language corpora for annotation in SIL FLEx:

<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/MRkIZE>

²⁷ We decided to place this introduction at the beginning of the workshop in order to orient the participants' attention to the nature of the platform where the workshop deliverables would be published so we could collectively take that into account as we listened to and discussed the presentations and subsequently formulated the structure of the workflows.

preservation of digitised textual materials and guides the users towards platforms, on which academic corpora can be stored together with their metadata and documentations. The last workflow is a guide to prepare minority or endangered language corpora for annotation in SIL FLEx (Fieldworks Standard Format Interlinear).²⁸ Since many under-represented languages have little digitally available data, the ability to add audio files can greatly improve the size and hence the quality of a corpus. In eight steps, or less, this workflow shows how to include such files, whether as audio files or as transcripts, in a corpus, to enhance its scope and representativity.

Further outcome and perspective

A corpus is the initial, and indispensable step in the whole digital pipeline that leads to computational text analysis. It depends on the digitisation of raw materials, the post-processing and cleaning of the digitisation outcome, should be aimed at or allowing further text processing and analysis. The most crucial takeaway from the event was perhaps related to the sheer diversity of the participants themselves, underscoring the benefits of having practitioners from different expertise, areas of interest and linguistic backgrounds attend the workshop. This has showcased the importance of how solutions to their own issues could be applied in other fields and languages, following the minimal computing approach, and thus preventing sparse resources from being wasted to often simply reinvent the wheel.²⁹ It was, in other words, a living example of a minimal computing approach. While the workflows have been the tangible outcomes of the workshop, the presentations which they are based upon, the discussions which followed them and the collaborative writing sprint at the end were necessary for us to be able to collectively produce such concise, but elaborate, workflows in half a day. Since resources (time, digitised materials, funding, personnel) are often the most important limiting factor for under-represented languages, the format of the workshop, as much as its outcomes, can serve as a basis for similar initiatives in the future.

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²⁸ See <https://software.sil.org/fieldworks/> [Retrieved 14 November 2024].

²⁹ See the slides of Till Grallert that were presented during the workshop and were made available by the author at <https://openarabicpe.github.io/slides/2024-dariah/#/title-slide> [Retrieved 9 November 2024].

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